

MICRO-MECHANICAL NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF TOUGHNESS IN MODEL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

We investigate the classical DCB test used to measure Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. We perform a numerical analysis of the development of the plastic zone near the tip of a crack induced in a unidirectional, thermoplastic matrix composite. The pure matrix is also studied for comparison purposes, the final aim being to shed some light on the mechanisms governing transfer of toughness. We use a non-linear finite element scheme implemented in the commercial code SAMCEF to compute the three-dimensional displacement and stress fields near the crack tip. The matrix and fiber reinforcement are discretized separately, assuming perfect bonding at the fiber/matrix interface. Results are discussed for a glass-fiber reinforced PAA matrix. The geometry of the plastic zone in the composite is found to be qualitatively very different from that of the pure matrix.

1. INTRODUCTION

The long-term objective of our work is to understand the transfer of fracture toughness between a thermoplastic polymer matrix and the corresponding fiber-reinforced composite. The topics we wish to investigate include (i) the effect of the reinforcement on the development of the matrix morphology, (ii) the influence of fiber-matrix interfacial properties, (iii) the impact of the reinforcement on the development of the plastic zone during mechanical testing for toughness properties, and (iv) the prediction of crack paths within the matrix micro-structure. This research program involves a combination of experimental and theoretical investigations, conducted within the framework of a collaborative project between our respective teams in Leuven and Louvain-la-Neuve. The present paper describes preliminary results on topic (iii).

Various aspects of Mode I interlaminar toughness of thermoplastic matrix composites have been reviewed recently (e.g. Sela and Ishai [1], Yee [2] and Hunston et al. [3]). The mechanisms responsible for the decrease of toughness relative to the pure matrix, which is observed for high toughness thermoplastics, are not well understood. A possible cause has been proposed on the basis of an hypothesized reduction of the size of the plastic zone (e.g. Yee [2]). The goal of the present work is to study the effect of the reinforcement on the development of the plastic zone in the classical DCB test. The analysis is based on detailed three-dimensional finite element calculations, and makes use of experimental data obtained by Goffaux [4]. We find that the geometrical nature of the plastic zone is much more complex than that assumed by Yee [2].

2. DCB SPECIMENS

A schematic of the Double Cantilever Beam test (DCB [5]) is shown in Fig. 1. Using this test, Goffaux [4] has obtained experimental data on Mode I toughness of an amorphous polyarylamid matrix (PAA), as well as Mode I interlaminar toughness of the unidirectional, glass-fiber reinforced, amorphous PAA. The data show a 50%+ decrease in toughness relative to the pure matrix.

Figure 1. Schematic of the DCB test.

The PAA matrix studied by Goffaux has a Young modulus of 3.6 GPa, a Poisson ratio of 0.35, and a yield stress of 73 MPa. The pure matrix DCB specimen is enclosed between two 3mm thick aluminum plates, with a Young modulus of 70 GPa, a Poisson ratio of 0.33 and a yield stress of 175 MPa. The overall geometrical dimensions of the specimen are $L = 150$ mm, $h = 1.25$ mm, $B = 17$ mm, and $e = 10$ mm. Goffaux [4] reports the following data at crack initiation: $a = 37$ mm, $v = 5.55$ mm, $P = 345$ N, $G_{Ic} = 4564$ J/m².

The DCB specimen for the composite has dimensions $L = 150$ mm, $h = 1.365$ mm, $B = 20$ mm, $e = 10$ mm. The continuous glass fibers have a diameter of 15 μ m, a volume fraction of 50%, a Young modulus of 75 GPa, and a Poisson ratio of 0.2. For the composite, Goffaux [4] reports the following data at crack initiation: $a = 38$ mm, $v = 18.2$ mm, $P = 65.3$ N, $G_{Ic} = 2040$ J/m².

We have used the above material and geometrical data for the numerical analysis of the DCB test.

3. MODELING APPROACH

A two-step modeling approach, illustrated in Fig. 2, is adopted in the present work.

In the first step, we study the complete, macroscopic DCB specimen by means of a two-dimensional, plane strain, finite element analysis. This computation treats the material as homogeneous. For the pure matrix specimen, we model the elasto-plastic behavior of the matrix and the aluminum plates by means of the Prandtl-Reuss-von Mises constitutive equation of incremental plasticity [6]. For the composite specimen, we treat the material as transversely isotropic and linear elastic. The latter assumption was deemed necessary in view of the lack of non-linear data for the composite under study. The homogenized elastic properties are derived from fiber and matrix properties by means of the composite cylinder micro-mechanical model [7]. This leads to a longitudinal Young modulus of 39.3 GPa, a transverse Young modulus of 9.9 GPa, and shear moduli approximately equal to 3.5 GPa.

The two-dimensional simulations have been performed with bi-quadratic elements. The mesh for the pure matrix specimen contains 42315 degrees of freedom, while that for the composite has 21728. By symmetry of the problem about the crack plane, only half of the specimen is discretized.

Figure 2. Macroscopic and microscopic computational domains.

The two-dimensional, macroscopic simulations conducted at the first step allow us to determine the displacement field at the boundary of a small neighborhood of the crack tip (Fig. 2). These computed displacements are used as boundary conditions for the second step, which involves a detailed, three-dimensional finite element analysis of the stress and displacement fields near the crack tip. Here, the matrix and fiber reinforcement are discretized separately, as shown in Fig. 2. The matrix is modeled as an elasto-plastic material, like in step 1, while the fibers are assumed linear elastic. Perfect bonding is assumed at the fiber/matrix interface.

Figure 3. Microscopic computational domain and boundary conditions.

The microscopic computational domain and boundary conditions are illustrated in Fig. 3. Symmetry about the crack plane and periodicity of the solution allow us to reduce the extent of the mesh (see also Fig. 2). Prescribed displacements are those computed in the two-dimensional macroscopic simulation.

The three-dimensional simulation of step 2 is of course not necessary for the pure matrix specimen, since in that case the solution is two-dimensional in the (x-z) plane. It is worth conducting it, however, in order to validate the transfer of information between the macroscopic and microscopic computational domains.

Along similar lines, we have considered an alternative way of performing the macro-micro transfer of information for the composite specimen. It consists of adding a layer of homogenized composite material adjacent to the faces where displacements are prescribed. Use of these "direct" and "smoothed-out" approaches have been found to produce equivalent results.

Since we model the macroscopic composite specimen as a linear elastic material, while the non-linearity of the matrix is taken into account, it will be impossible to compare *quantitatively* the non-linear microscopic results obtained for the pure matrix and the composite specimens. The discussion of results given below will rather focus on the main *qualitative* differences, in terms of the development of the plastic zone near the crack tip. This is appropriate, since the proper consideration of the composite's macroscopic non-linear behavior (in step 1) would only affect the actual values of the displacements prescribed to the microscopic analysis (in step 2).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Pure Matrix

Let us first consider the results obtained for the pure matrix, under the load conditions of Section 2. The three-dimensional, microscopic computational domain has the following dimensions (Fig. 3) :

$l = 831 \mu\text{m}$, $b = 605 \mu\text{m}$, $t = 9.4 \mu\text{m}$, crack tip located at $x = 360 \mu\text{m}$.

The finite element mesh contains 5940 tri-linear elements, and a total of 21736 degrees of freedom. The simulation was run on a CONVEX C3820, with a total CPU time of about one hour.

Figure 4. Plastic zone for the pure matrix and finite element mesh near the crack tip.

Figure 4 shows the computed plastic zone as well as a partial view of the finite element mesh near the crack tip. Only one half of the plastic zone is shown, in view of the symmetry about the plane of the crack. The plastic zone has an oval shape, and it is contained within a rectangle 204 μm long and 222 μm high. A simulation using a coarser finite element mesh shows that these figures have converged, in the finite element sense, within about 2%. The entire plastic zone occupies about 1.9% of the macroscopic DCB sample.

4.2 Composite

We have used several microscopic computational domains, with an increasing number of fibers, in an attempt to capture the entire plastic zone within the composite. So far, up to 31 fibers have been used in the height of the microscopic mesh (Fig. 2). As we shall see, this is not enough to enclose the plastic zone completely.

In view of the complexity of the finite element simulations, several tests have been performed in order to assess the accuracy of the numerical results and the validity of the boundary conditions. The results for 15 fibers have been checked with care by means of a mesh refinement study involving two grids with 26143 and 63433 degrees of freedom, respectively. The transfer of information from the two-dimensional, homogeneous model (step 1) to the three-dimensional, heterogeneous simulation (step 2) has been checked by comparing, for the case of 31 fibers, the results with and without a homogenized layer at the boundary of the microscopic mesh.

We describe the results obtained under the load conditions of Section 2 with a 27 fibre microscopic mesh, including a homogenized layer. The computational domain has the following dimensions :

$l = 1187 \mu\text{m}$, $b = 583 \mu\text{m}$, $t = 9.4 \mu\text{m}$, crack tip located at $x = 360 \mu\text{m}$.

The mesh contains 20832 elements and 58426 degrees of freedom. The simulation time on a CONVEX C3820 is about 4 hours.

We find that the plastic zone has a rather complex three-dimensional geometry.

Figure 5. Trace of the plastic zone in the $y = 0$ plane, in the neighborhood of the crack tip (Fig. 3).

Figure 5 shows the trace of the plastic zone in the $y = 0$ plane, superimposed on the finite element mesh. The results for the back plane $y = t$ are illustrated in Fig. 6. On the $y = 0$ plane, the plastic zone is confined to the neighborhood of the crack tip. It only extends 138 μm wide and 100 μm high. This approximately corresponds to a height of 6 fibers.

Figure 6. Trace of the plastic zone in the $y = t$ plane (cfr Fig. 3). The entire microscopic computational domain is shown, with the dashed region denoting the homogenized layer.

The results are very different in the back plane, where the plastic zone is seen to occupy a large fraction of the computational domain. Although the height of the microscopic mesh is almost half of that of the macroscopic DCB sample, the plastic zone has not yet reached its maximum height.

Figure 7. Plastic zone in a cut located at the crack tip, $x = 360 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 6).

The complexity of the above three-dimensional results is better comprehended by inspection of Figs. 7-8, where we show the development of the plastic zone in transverse cuts located at the crack tip, and away from it (Fig. 6). These figures show the plastic zone as dashed regions superimposed on the finite element mesh. The results are shown for the first 15 fibers, numbered from the crack plane down. For clarity, heavy semi-circular arcs are used to locate the fiber-matrix interface.

Figure 8. Plastic zone in a cut located away from the crack tip, $x = 680 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 6).

Below the crack tip, the plastic zone occupies almost all the matrix phase until Fiber #5. From Fiber #6 to Fiber #14, the plastic zone is confined in a small region between consecutive fibers. Finally, the behavior is purely elastic below Fiber #14.

In the cut located away from the crack tip, we observe elastic behavior between Fibers #1 and #3. Below Fiber #3, plastic deformations are predicted in the regions separating consecutive fibers.

5. CONCLUSION

Micro-mechanical finite element simulations have been carried out to predict the development of the plastic zone in the DCB test applied to a unidirectional, thermoplastic polymer composite. The results show that the plastic zone has an intricate, fully three-dimensional geometry that is qualitatively very different from that obtained with the pure matrix. In particular, the plastic zone is *not* found to be constrained by the reinforcement, as it is sometimes argued in the literature to explain observed decreases in toughness relative to the pure matrix. Although a quantitative comparison remains to be carried out between the simulation results for the pure matrix and composite specimens, it is likely that the proposed numerical approach will shed some light on the mechanisms governing toughness of fiber-reinforced composites.

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